

A SHEAR STRENGTH MODEL FOR REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS WITH U-WRAPPED FRCM COMPOSITES BASED ON THE COMPRESSION CHORD CAPACITY MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new procedure to determine the different shear strength contributions of reinforced concrete (RC) beams strengthened with U-wrapped externally bonded (EB) fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM) composite. A main shear crack, named the critical shear crack (CSC), is assumed. The shear strength contributions are related to the CSC width evolution. The relationship between concrete contribution and CSC width is a hyperbolic function with a horizontal asymptote based on the compression chord capacity model (CCCM). Using a Mörsch truss model, the procedure accounts for the presence of internal steel stirrups and EB FRCM that is modelled considering its bond behavior and tensile strength. The procedure allows for predicting the total shear strength and the different contributions, as shown by comparison between the analytical and experimental results of a beam taken from the literature.

KEYWORDS

Bond; compression chord capacity model (CCCM); fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM) composite; shear; strengthening

INTRODUCTION

Existing reinforced concrete (RC) structures often need to be repaired or strengthened during their service life due to construction defects, increase of applied load, extreme events, etc. Within this context, shear strengthening is considered a critical issue for structural elements with insufficient or no shear reinforcement due to the sudden and brittle nature of shear failure.

Externally bonded (EB) fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM) composite, also known as fabric-reinforced cementitious matrix composite or textile-reinforced mortar (TRM), is an alternative to the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composite to retrofit RC structural members such as beams and columns. FRCM has some advantages over FRP: i) it has a higher resistance to (relatively) high temperature, since no epoxy resins are used; ii) it can be applied to wet surfaces and at low temperatures; iii) it is compatible with concrete and masonry substrates; iv) it allows transpiration; v) it does not suffer from sunlight exposure; and vi) it does not produce toxic smoke in the case of fire (Triantafillou and Papanicolaou 2006; Jung et al. 2015).

The work started in 1998 (Wiberg 2003) explored the use of EB FRCM for shear strengthening of RC beams and proved the potential of this strengthening technique. Since then, various models for the design and assessment of shear strengthening by EB FRCM have been proposed. There are two main groups of models to evaluate the shear strength provided by FRCM. The first is based on fiber properties (Triantafillou and Papanicolaou 2006; Escrig et al. 2015), whereas the second on composite properties (ACI 549.4R 2013; Ombres 2015; CNR-DT 215/2018 2018). Currently, there are only two guidelines, CNR-DT 215 and ACI 549.4R, for the design of EB FRCM for strengthening concrete structures. The former belongs to the first group, while the latter to the second group.

All models available in the literature consider that the contribution to the shear strength of the external reinforcement V_f can be simply added to the shear strength of the unreinforced RC element V_{um} . Thus, the design equation common to all models to compute the nominal shear strength V_n is given by Eq. 1:

$$V_n = V_{um} + V_f = V_c + V_s + V_f \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where V_c and V_s are the concrete and steel shear strength contributions, respectively.

In practical applications, adopting the fully wrapped strengthening configuration to beams and other shear-bending elements can be challenging due to construction complexities involved. For example, the presence of the slab in cast-in-place concrete floor systems often restricts access to the beam top surface. As a result, the U-wrapped layout is often employed. D'Antino et al. proposed a mechanics-based model to evaluate the shear strength contribution (V_f) of FRCM composites when applied in a U-wrapped configuration around RC members (D'Antino et al. 2019). This model does not rely on empirical coefficients and can be applied to any FRCM composite with known bond behavior and tensile strength. Some aspects of this model are further explained in the subsection, *U-wrapped EB FRCM Contribution*.

The present study is intended to deepen the understanding of the shear strength of RC elements strengthened with U-wrapped EB FRCM. For this purpose, the evolution of each contribution to the shear strength shown in Eq. 1 was studied with respect to the opening of a main shear crack, named the critical shear crack (CSC). With this analysis, the objective is twofold. On the one hand, it allows for evaluating the shear strength by considering strain/crack opening compatibility between the concrete, steel, and composite contributions. Furthermore, if these contributions co-occur, a rational estimation may be deduced. On the other hand, it allows for determining the evolution of each contribution with the CSC opening. This aspect has clear advantages for the design of this type of strengthening, e.g., for limiting the shear crack width thus improving durability.

In order to carry out this study, the following steps were followed:

1. A CSC pattern was established based on observations from experimental tests reported in the literature.
2. An estimation based on mechanical considerations of the shear strength contributions that also occur in unstrengthened elements (V_c and V_s of Eq. 1) was developed.
3. A model that describes the evolution of the shear strength contribution of U-wrapped EB FRCM versus the CSC opening was formulated.
4. The model was applied to a beam reported in the literature, and the results obtained were compared.

CRITICAL SHEAR CRACK PATTERN OBSERVED IN U-WRAPPED EB FRCM RC STRENGTHENED ELEMENTS

The CSC of RC slender beams without shear reinforcement or with low to medium amounts of shear reinforcement (usually associated with rectangular sections) has been studied extensively over the last century (see Zararis and Papadakis 2001; Park et al. 2006; Fernández et al. 2015; Marí et al. 2015, among others). In general, the CSC is defined in two branches. The first branch develops in the tensile zone due to bending and often starts from a vertical crack. The second branch, located in the compressed flexural chord, starts from the end of the first branch (at the height of the neutral axis) and propagates towards the point of load application (if it exists) with a much shallower angle than the first branch. The development of this second branch is typically associated with the shear failure of the beam if the beam does not have stirrups. These two branches are sometimes joined by a well-defined vertex and sometimes by a curve that may be tangent to both branches. This type of CSC does not necessarily occur in RC beams with medium to high amounts of shear reinforcement (usually associated with T or double-T sections) where shear cracking usually appears as multiple cracks distributed over a region of the shear span. However, it sometimes occurs as a superior envelope to distributed cracking (Figure 1a).

In order to conduct this research, CSC shapes from numerous experimental studies (Triantafillou and Papanicolaou 2006; Brückneret al. 2008; Blanksvärdet al. n.d.; Al-Salloum et al. 2011; Contamine et al. 2013; Azam and Soudki 2014; Baggio et al. 2014; Tzoura and Triantafillou 2016; Escrig et al. 2015; Jung et al. 2015; Ombres 2015; Tetta et al. 2015; Trapko et al. 2015; Gonzalez-Libreros et al. 2017) of RC beams strengthened by EB FRCM were reviewed. In general, all experimental campaigns reviewed exhibited CSCs like those previously described (see e.g. Figure 1a, Trapko et al. 2015). In addition to this observation, some particularities were noted: i) in some cases where EB FRCM anchorages were applied at the top of the beam, the crack tended to pass through the anchorage, probably because it is a point where the concrete section has been reduced (Figure 1b, (Baggio et al. 2014)); ii) in some cases where continuous EB FRCM reinforcement was applied to only part of the shear span, the CSC tended to develop in the part without EB FRCM (Figure 1c, Escrig et al. 2015); and iii) in tests with cyclic loading, where the direction of the shear force changed during the test, more damage and cracks in opposite directions were observed, as the tensioned and compressed zones alternated during the test (Figure 1d, Tzoura and Triantafillou 2016). Despite these particularities, the most commonly observed CSC pattern was similar to the one described in the literature for elements with no or with low amounts of shear reinforcement. Note that in the examples illustrated in Figure 1, the two branches of the CSC described above were observed.

Figure 1: CSC pattern observed in RC beams strengthened with EB FRCM

SHEAR STRENGTH EVOLUTION OF CONCRETE AND STEEL CONTRIBUTIONS

Computing the shear strength of RC beams as the sum of the concrete and steel contributions and how standards address this problem have been long debated. In this regard, Poldon et al. (2023) recently showed, by using distributed fiber-optic sensors (DFOS) to measure the strain along the reinforcing bars, that the stirrups (and, by extension, the Ritter-Mörsh model or V_s) were not the sole contributor to resisting vertical shear in the studied beams, contrary to the assumptions behind the Eurocode 2 (EN 1992-1-1:2004) shear provisions.

Figure 2a shows the total vertical shear force supported by the stirrups (V_s) determined by adding the forces in the stirrups crossing a shear crack during tests performed by Poldon et al. (2023). Note that each curve in Figure 2a is associated to a specific crack of a certain beam. Each shear crack analyzed by the authors supports a shear force that, in all but one case (i.e., JP-2 C1), is less than the total shear force supported (Figure 2a). The coexistence of two contributions is thus demonstrated by equilibrium, which could be simplified schematically according to Figure 2b. The deviations from this simplification observed for some of the beams may be due to the fact that, at the beginning of the crack formation, the crack does not cross many stirrups limiting V_s , or it does not cross the direct strut from the loading point to the support promoting the arch effect, and therefore, enlarging V_c (e.g., JP-2 C2) (note that the opposite can also occur, see e.g., JP-2 C1). In general, the experimental measurement is similar to the approach proposed by Fenwick and Paulay in the late sixties (Fenwick 1966; Fenwick and Paulay 1968) (Figure 2c), which was obtained by ad hoc tests for each shear-transfer action. Nevertheless, in Poldon et al.'s study, the contribution of V_c during the tests is decreasing (in agreement with the analysis of Fernandez et al. 2015) that the wider the crack opening, the lower the value of V_c , as discussed in the next subsection).

Figure 2: V_c and V_s evolution during a beam shear test

Concrete Contribution

In 1968, Fenwick and Paulay (1968) were the first to identify and experimentally quantify the different beam shear transfer mechanisms: shearing stresses across the flexural compression zone, aggregate interlock across a crack, dowel action, and tensile force in the web reinforcement. Since then, much work has been done to quantify each of the shear resistance mechanisms, the first three of

which together form the so-called shear contribution of concrete. In 2013, Campana et al. (2013), based on the aggregate interlock studies of Walraven (1981), Guidotti (2010), and Ulaga (2003), analyzed the crack kinematics and evaluated the contributions of each shear transfer action across the CSC.

Following Campana et al.'s procedure and applying digital image correlation, Cavagnis et al. (2018) and Huber et al. (2016), among others, performed a similar study in different phases of shear tests. Furthermore, Cavagnis analyzed the evolution of shear transfer actions in several tests. In those with a/d (where a is the shear span, and d is the effective depth) from 5.67 to 6.92, aggregate interlock was the main shear transfer action given the distance of the critical crack from the support. In the SC68-test with an $a/d=2.52$, a significant redistribution between shear transfer actions was observed, from shear stresses in the compressed zone to aggregate interlock in the last 4.5% increase of the total load.

Montoya et al. (2023) followed a similar procedure increasing the analyzed steps (between 2700 to 4240 steps for each test) and focusing on the aggregate interlock. They observed that close to failure (for loads higher than 90% and 98% of the failure load), the formation of the second branch of the critical shear crack (State IIa in Figure 3b), and its associated sliding, heavily increments the aggregate interlock contribution to the shear strength (Figure 3a-c). After the formation of the second branch of the CSC, the aggregate interlock contribution ranged from 31.9% to 85% at failure.

This substantial redistribution of shear-transfer actions (between the final 2% and 10% of load) supports that those models based on equilibrium, at an instant in which the first branch of the critical shear crack has fully developed (Marí et al. 2015; Cladera et al. 2016) (State Ia Figure 3b), and those models that consider the aggregate interlock after the developing of the second branch (State IIa in Figure 3b) as the main shear-transfer action (Fernández et al. 2015), are not contradictory. Furthermore, both may represent two very close states before and after the observed redistribution close to failure.

Figure 3: Evolution of the aggregate interlock contribution to the shear strength during a beam shear test. Adapted from (Montoya-Coronado et al. 2023)

Given that these redistributions are so close to shear failure (ultimate limit state, ULS), it may happen that different approximations (of a mechanical nature) may provide similar results even if based on different hypotheses.

Regarding the variation of shear strength versus the critical crack width, Fernández et al. (2015) reviewed the various potential shear-transfer actions through an analytical integration of the stresses developed at a two-branched CSC and accounting for the member kinematics. According to this

analysis, all the shear transfer actions are functions (hyperbolic) of the longitudinal strain ε multiplied by the effective depth d and divided by the aggregate size d_{g0} (which is constant), that is proportional to the CSC width ω .

Figure 4: Analysis of the different shear-transfer actions versus crack opening in a RC beam. Adapted from (Fernández et al. 2015)

Steel Contribution

In 1909, Mörsch (1909) proposed a truss model in which the struts were compressed concrete, and the ties were tensioned steel bars (stirrups or longitudinal bars, Figure 5a). This model has been useful for structural analysis and design to this day. In 1961, Leonhardt and Walther (1961) observed that this model predicted the behavior of the stirrups once the concrete had cracked (Figure 5b). Both Collins et al. (2008) and Eurocode 2 (2004) proposed a proportional value $d-c$ (where d is the effective depth, and c is the depth of the neutral axis) as an approximation of the distance s between primary flexural cracks (which subsequently become flexural-shear cracks). Collins et al. (2008) proposed $d-c$ as the mean crack spacing, and Eurocode 2, being a design standard, provides $1.3(d-c)$ as the maximum crack spacing.

Assuming that all the strain ε of an RC element occurs in the crack and using: a) the Mörsch truss model, b) the distance between main cracks proposed by Collins et al. (2008), and c) the angle of inclination of the diagonally compressed struts θ proposed by Cladera et al. (2016) (see Figure 5c), a linear relationship before stirrup yielding can be established between the width of the CSC ω and the vertical shear force supported by the stirrups (i.e., the steel contribution V_s). This relationship is given by Eq. 2:

$$\omega = s + \varepsilon = (d - c) \sin \theta \frac{V_s}{E_s A_{St} 0.85d} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where E_s is the stirrup modulus of elasticity, and A_{St} is the web reinforcement cross-sectional area. After yielding, the force provided by stirrups is considered constant up to stirrup failure.

Figure 5: Simplification of the V_s - ω relationship during a beam shear test, based on a) the Morsch truss model, adapted from (Morsch 1909); b) Leonhardt and Walther observations, adapted from (Leonhardt and Walther 1961); c) distance between cracks s proposed by Collins et al. (2008) and inclination of the diagonally compressed struts θ proposed by Cladera et al. (2016)

U-wrapped EB-FRCM Contribution

The shear strength contribution provided by U-wrapped EB FRCM V_f can be computed assuming a Morsch truss model analogous to that considered for the internal steel shear strength contribution. D'Antino et al. (2019) proposed an analytical model, adopted by the Italian CNR-DT 215, that provides V_f accounting for the bond behavior and tensile strength of the FRCM considered. Starting from this model, Bertolli and D'Antino (2022b) formulated an analytical procedure to relate the stress in the U-wrapped FRCM to the critical shear crack opening. This procedure was based on a rigid-trilinear cohesive material law (CML) that was used to solve the bond differential equation (Bertolli and D'Antino 2022a), providing the FRCM response along the CSC for any value of the crack width ω . Details of the procedure and results obtained can be found in (Bertolli and D'Antino 2022b).

ANALYSIS OF AN RC BEAM WITH EB FRCM TAKEN FROM THE LITERATURE

The L_1_Ave RC beam tested by Loreto et al. (2015) was analyzed using the approaches presented. The main characteristics of the tested beam are reported in Figure 6. The longitudinal tensile reinforcement consisted of four 19.1 mm diameter micro-composite multi-structural formable steel (MMFX) bars placed in two rows with a nominal area of 286 mm². The nominal yield strength of the MMFX bars was 690 MPa, and the modulus of elasticity was 200 GPa. The stirrups were made of reinforcing steel with diameter of 5.7 mm, nominal area of 26 mm², and spacing of 125 mm. Two longitudinal 9.5 mm diameter reinforcing steel bars were located in at the compressed side. The bars used for the stirrups and longitudinal compression reinforcement had a nominal yield strength of 276 MPa and a modulus of elasticity of 200 GPa. The average concrete strength was 29.13 MPa, and its modulus of elasticity was 29.5 GPa.

The beam was strengthened with one layer of a U-wrapped polyparaphenylene benzobisoxazole (PBO) FRCM composite. The PBO textile was a bidirectional open-mesh fabric with fibers spaced at 10 mm on center in the primary direction (PD) and at 17.5 mm on center in the secondary direction (SD). The nominal thickness of the fabric was 0.046 mm in the PD and 0.011 mm in the SD. The fabric was embedded within two 1.5–2 mm thick layers of a cement-based mortar.

The mechanical properties of the FRCM were obtained with clevis-grip tensile tests of composite coupons following the provisions of (AC434 2018). Accordingly, the modulus of elasticity of the cracked specimen (E_f) was 127 GPa, the ultimate tensile strength (f_{fu}) was 1664 MPa, and the ultimate tensile strain (ϵ_{fu}) was 0.0176 mm/mm. This provided a design tensile strain in the FRCM shear reinforcement (ϵ_{fv}) equal to 0.004 mm/mm and a design tensile strength ($f_{fv} = E_f \epsilon_{fv}$) equal to 510 MPa. More information about the specimen is reported in (Loreto et al. 2015).

Figure 6: Test specimen analysed. Adapted from (Loreto et al. 2015)

The ultimate shear strength of the tested beam was 101.56 kN. Considering the procedure provided by ACI 549.4R, which adopts the mechanical properties of FRCM coupons tested using the clevis-grip set-up (AC434 2018), a shear strength of 68.43 kN was computed. Adopting the procedure proposed in this paper, the ultimate shear strength is 98.41 kN. Note that the proposed model was developed by making only mechanical considerations and adopting some simplifications. Moreover, the proposed method allows for studying the evolution of the shear strength contributions shown in Eq. 1.

As suggested by Fernandez et al. (2015), a hyperbolic function was used to predict the behavior of the concrete shear strength contribution V_c . However, their proposal was developed for RC elements without shear reinforcement, where the CSC width is controlled only in the beam lower part by the longitudinal reinforcement. In this paper, a hyperbolic function that starts from the concrete shear strength for a curvature or crack width equal to 0 (deduced by the CSC Theory $V_{CSC(\psi=0)}$ mechanically explained by Fernández et al. (2015)) and with a horizontal asymptote equal to the shear contribution of the concrete at the ULS (deduced by the CCCM V_{CCCM} (Cladera et al. 2016)), was adopted. The proposed function is given by Eq. 3:

$$V_c = \frac{1}{(1.5\omega+k)^2} + V_{CCCM} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where k is a constant to ensure that for $\omega=0$, $V_c = V_{CSC(\psi=0)}$.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the different shear strength contributions, and the sum of the set of shear contributions which is the predicted shear strength $V_{predicted}$ as a function of the CSC width ω_{CSC} . In this figure, it can be seen that the correlation between V_c and V_s is similar to that observed by

Poldon et al. (2023), where the V_s contribution increases with respect to the V_c contribution during the test, and the three contributions are compatible with the CSC width that develops up to the debonding failure of the U-wrapped FRCM. This aspect is consistent with the approach of Eq. 1 (additive for the three shear strength contributions).

Figure 7: Analysis of the different shear strength contributions vs CSC width ω_{CSC}

In Figure 7, it can be observed that the steel shear strength contribution (red shaded region) has a peak when the stirrups yield. It is important to emphasize that the approximation of the distance between primary cracks (although adequate, it is still an approximation to a highly variable phenomenon) affects the peak position. If the actual distance between primary cracks were lower or higher than the prediction, this peak would be shifted to the right or left, respectively. However, this would not affect the predicted ultimate shear strength.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the different shear strength contributions of RC beams strengthened with U-wrapped EB FRCM were analyzed proposing an analytical model based only on mechanical considerations. The concrete contribution was modelled as a hyperbolic curve that starts based on the critical shear crack theory and has a horizontal asymptote deduced by the compression chord capacity model. The model accounted for the bond behavior of the U-wrapped EB FRCM and for the contribution of internal steel stirrups. Both increase their shear strength contribution when the CSC width grows. An approximation for the distance between primary cracks (high variability value) was assumed, and the steel stirrup behavior during the analysis depended on this value. However, the strength at ULS was not affected by this parameter.

For the FRCM shear strength contribution, a Mörsh truss model and an analytical approach were proposed to describe the distribution of stresses developing in the FRCM shear reinforcement bridging the CSC to provide an accurate estimation of the composite shear strength contribution. Although the results should be considered with caution and more tested elements should be analyzed, the proposal allows to: a) predict the shear strength of the specimen, b) predict the shear strength contributions for different CSC widths, and c) study the evolution of crack opening due to shear. This procedure can be used to increase the current knowledge on the possible interaction between internal and external shear reinforcement for RC elements reinforced with U-wrapped EB FRCM. Thus, it may become a valuable tool for developing structural design assessments in engineering practice.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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